

FREE-EDGE STRESSES IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES UNDER MECHANICAL LOADING

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1 General Introduction

For laminated composites, it is well-known that at the free edges interlaminar stresses arise from the mismatch of elastic properties between layers. Hence, the stress distribution in the vicinity of the free edges is three dimensional (3D) state even though the laminates are only subjected to in-plane loading [1, 2].

The interlaminar stresses are important because they have a marked effect on the failure strengths of composite laminates. Accurate determination of interlaminar stresses near the free edge is therefore crucial to correctly describe the laminate behavior and to prevent its early failure, notably the delamination onset. This paper analyzes the stress-strain conditions at free edges of the laminates and using known delamination Tsai criteria predicts delamination occurrence.

2 Stress analysis at free edges of laminates

The relation between stress and strain in a laminate layer away from the free edge is represented by the following relation

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_x &= \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} - \nu_{yx} \cdot \frac{\sigma_y}{E_y} - m_x \cdot \tau_{xy} \\ \varepsilon_y &= \frac{\sigma_y}{E_y} - \nu_{xy} \cdot \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x} - m_y \cdot \tau_{xy} \\ \gamma_{xy} &= -m_x \cdot \sigma_x - m_y \cdot \sigma_y + \frac{\tau_{xy}}{G_{xy}}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

Coefficients m_x and m_y in the previous equation represent the coefficients of mutual influence and

can be expressed as a function of fiber angle (θ), Young's module (E_1, E_2), shear modulus (G_{12}) and Poisson ratios (ν_{12}, ν_{21}) in the direction of the principal axes. $\varepsilon_{ij}, \sigma_{ij}$, ($i, j = x, y$) are the strain and stress components for the plane stress state. Near the free edges values of normal stress can have a large value which can cause damage to the structures at these locations, or can cause the separation of the lamina, a phenomenon known as delamination. In order to obtain accurate stress distribution in these areas a complete three-dimensional analysis has to be performed [3-5].

The case of $[0^0/90^0]_s$ laminate is initially analyzed. Considering this stack up sequence, when laminas are not bound, under axial tension, there would be different axial deformation due to different Poisson ratios.

Fig.1 Stresses near free edge of $[0^0/90^0]_s$ laminate under axial loading

By tying these laminae into the laminate, under axial tension, they must have the same axial strain. Such stress and strain state is achieved by τ_{zy} stress component, which stretches the laminate 0^0 and compresses 90^0 laminate. Analyzing the elementary particle of 0^0 laminate near the free edge, it follows that shear flow component q_{zy} is balanced with force per unit length f_y . In order to satisfy equilibrium of moments in the "YZ" plane, the distribution of normal stress σ_z must be such that

there is no resultant force in the z direction, and that the moment of forces per unit length f_z is of the opposite direction from the torque caused by forces q_{zy} and f_y . For a lamina which is not loaded in the direction of principal axes in general, in the case of axial tension both shear and axial deformations will occur. Analyzing two laminas of the same material (fiber, matrix, and the same volume fraction of components) under axial tension, with the fibers in the direction of $[+\theta]$ and $[-\theta]$, when laminas are not interconnected, it can be concluded that these laminas have the same shear deformations of opposite signs. In the event that the foregoing laminas $[+\theta / -\theta]$ are merged into a whole (laminate), shear deformations must be zero. The only way to achieve this kind of stress-strain state is if there is a stress component τ_{zx} . Moments of shear flow q_{zx} must balance the shear flow q_{xy} .

Fig.2 $[+\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminate deformations under axial loading

2.1 Numerical analysis

In order to obtain accurate distribution of these stresses, three-dimensional stress and strain analysis was carried out by finite element analysis. The finite element model mesh is presented. In present model eight nodal hexahedron elements are used for meshing each lamina.

Fig.3. Finite element model for stress distribution at free edges for $[+\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminate under axial loading

For $[0^0/90^0]_s$ laminate shear stress τ_{zy} reaches its extreme values near the free edges of the laminate, while it is equal to zero in the central zone of the laminate. Shear stresses τ_{zx} are equal to zero in the central zone and near the edges, while the normal stresses σ_z are zero in the central zone, and reach their extreme values near the free edge of the laminate.

The analysis results are shown in the following figures (Fig.4 to Fig. 10).

Fig.4 σ_z normal stress component near free edge of $[90/0]_s$ laminate under axial loading

Fig. 5 Stresses near free edge of $[0^0/90^0]_s$ laminate under axial loading. σ_z stress component

Fig. 6 Stresses near free edge of $[0^0/90^0]_s$ laminate under axial loading. τ_{zy} stress component

In the case of $[+\theta /-\theta]_s$ stacking, shear stress components τ_{zx} are equal to zero in most of the central part of the laminate. Approaching the edges, the value of these stresses rises sharply, reaching extreme values very close to the free edge. τ_{xy} components have a constant value in most of the central zone of the laminate, while close to the free edge of the laminate value rapidly decreases to zero.

Fig. 7 σ_z normal stress component near free edge of $[+\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminate under axial loading

Figure 8 Distribution of σ_z normal stress component near free edge of $[+\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminate under axial loading

Fig.9 Distribution of τ_{xz} shear stress component near free edge of the $[+\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminate under axial loading

Fig 10 Distribution of τ_{yz} shear stress component near free edge of the $[+\theta/-\theta]_s$ laminate under axial loading

2.2 Delamination prediction

Based on the known three-dimensional stress state, and known criteria applicable to the failure analysis of composite structures, it is necessary to check the breakdown of the structure, and verify whether the delamination will occur at free edges of the composite. According to the Tsai's criterion [6] delamination in the composite will occur when the following relation is satisfied (2):

$$\frac{\sigma_x^2 - \sigma_x \cdot \sigma_z}{X_t^2} + \frac{\sigma_x^2}{Z^2} + \frac{\tau_{zx}^2}{R^2} = 1 \quad (2)$$

In the previous relation σ_x , σ_z , τ_{zx} are three-dimensional stress components in the appropriate directions for the considered laminate position (close to free edge), and X_t , Z and R are allowed stresses for the laminate along the "x" direction "z" and allowable shear stress. The values of allowable stresses are determined by experiment.

3 Conclusion

Stresses near free edges of loaded composite laminate can have very large values, which might lead to the occurrence of delamination of the

laminate layers and thus lead to the failure of the entire structure. In this study a method to determine all stress components near the free edge of the laminate. In the case of $[\theta /-\theta]_s$ laminates, shear stress components τ_{zx} are equal to zero in most of the central part of the laminate. Approaching the edges, the value of the stresses rises sharply, reaching extreme values very close to the free edge. τ_{xy} shear stress components have a constant value in most of the central zone of the laminate, while decreasing to zero near free edges. When stacking $[0 / 90]_s$ is considered the shear stress component τ_{zy} reach its extreme value near the free edges of the laminate, while being zero in the central zone of the laminate. Shear stresses τ_{zx} are equal to zero in the central zone and near the free edges while the normal stress σ_z is zero in the central zone, and reach its extreme values near the free edge of the laminate. Using methodology presented in this paper is possible to accurately determine the three-dimensional stress state near the edges and verify structure bearing capacity using Tsai's criteria of delamination.

4 References

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